

INTERACTION OF DISLOCATIONS WITH RESIDUAL STRESSES IN PARTICLE REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Residual stresses arising from the elastic and plastic deformation of the matrix in the vicinity of particles in reinforced composites can interact with dislocations and other crystal defects. Using the effective medium theory, the stress fields associated with the elastic and plastic zones surrounding spherical particles have previously been calculated. In this work this solution is applied to the description of plastic deformation of the composite by determining the force exerted on dislocations by these stresses. This relates to the influence of these stresses on plastic flow. Also, the effect of the internal stress fields on the propagation of cracks is estimated by determining the effective force on the crack front due to the residual stress fields. These results will assist in the design of heat treatments of composites to control the mechanical properties.

INTRODUCTION

When a particle reinforced metal-matrix composite (MMC) is cooled down from its fabrication temperature, where the internal stress is zero, the relative thermal expansion of the reinforcing inclusions and the metal matrix will cause the formation of significant residual stresses both in the particle and in the adjacent matrix. A model of this process has recently been formulated by one of us and collaborators, which enables the form and magnitude of these stresses to be obtained when the particles are all spherical, of equal size and randomly distributed in the matrix[1]. The purpose of this study is to examine these stresses and their interactions with defects such as dislocations and cracks in the matrix and thereby to estimate the effects of the stresses on the mechanical properties such as flow stress and fracture toughness of the MMC.

SOLUTION TO THE ELASTIC-PLASTIC PROBLEM

Let be A the radius of a reinforcing particle surrounded by a concentric spherical matrix region of radius, B such that the volume fraction of particles in the MMC is A^3/B^3 . Then Bullough and Davis[1] have shown that cooling from the stress-free equilibrium state through ΔT degrees can cause yielding of the matrix, resulting in three concentric spherical regions: the particle, $0 < r < A$; the plastic region, $A < r < R$, of the matrix between the particle and the elastic zone, and an elastic zone, $R < r < B$, where r is the radial distance from the center of the particle to a general point. The residual stress field in the elastic zone has the following spherical polar components:

$$p_{rr}(r) = \frac{2p_y}{3} \left(\frac{R}{B} \right)^3 \left(1 - \frac{B^3}{r^3} \right) \quad (1)$$

and

$$p_{\theta\theta} = p_{\phi\phi} = \frac{2p_y}{3} \left(\frac{R}{B} \right)^3 \left(1 + \frac{B^3}{2r^3} \right), \quad (2)$$

where R is the value of r at which yield occurs. At the interface of the elastic and plastic zones r = R and the von Mises yield criterion holds,

$$p_{rr} - p_{\theta\theta} = p_y, \quad (3)$$

with p_y representing the tensile yield stress. When yield occurs the value of R is given by the solution to

$$\ln \left(\frac{R}{A} \right)^3 + 1 - \left(\frac{R}{B} \right)^3 + \left(\frac{R}{A} \right)^3 \frac{K_p(3K+4\mu)}{4\mu(K-K_p)} - \frac{9KK_p(\alpha-\alpha_p)\Delta T}{2 p_y (KK_p)} = 0, \quad (4)$$

where μ and K are the shear modulus and bulk modulus of the matrix and α is the thermal expansion coefficient of the matrix. The subscript p indicates the corresponding properties of the particle. If yield does not occur at the matrix-particle interface, then R=A in Eqns. (1) and (2) and p_y should be expressed in terms of ΔT by formally setting R=A in Eqn. (4).

INTERACTION WITH DISLOCATIONS

To derive the required interactions between the stresses in Eqns. (1) and (2) and various defects in the elastic region it is convenient to express these stresses in the Cartesian coordinate system (x_1, x_2, x_3) with origin at the center of the particle, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Spherical and Cartesian Coordinate System

The Cartesian components of the stress tensor corresponding to Eqns. (1) and (2) are

$$p_{ij} = \frac{p_y}{3} \left(\frac{R}{B} \right)^3 \left[2\delta_{ij} + \frac{B^3}{r^3} \left(\delta_{ij} - \frac{3x_i x_j}{r^2} \right) \right], \quad (5)$$

where $r^2 = [x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2]$.

Without loss of generality let us consider a slip plane in the crystalline matrix region that is parallel to the x_1, x_2 plane and intersects the x_3 axis at $x_3 = z$. For this slip plane to intersect the elastic zone of the composite sphere we must have

$$R \leq z \leq B. \quad (6)$$

The radius of the circle in the elastic zone intersected by the slip plane is

$$R_s = \sqrt{B^2 - z^2}. \quad (7)$$

If a glide dislocation is identified as a chord of this circular region of the slip plane, as shown in Figure 2, the points on the chord have Cartesian coordinates (x, y, z) , where $x_3 = z$ (constrained by Eqn. (6)) defines the radial position of the slip plane above the particle. Also $x_2 = y$ defines the location of the dislocation such that

$$0 \leq |y| \leq \sqrt{B^2 - z^2} \quad (8)$$

and $x_1 = x$, where

$$0 \leq |x| \leq \sqrt{B^2 - y^2 - z^2} \quad (9)$$

defines the points on the dislocation when y and z are fixed.

Figure 2. Dislocation and Particle Geometry

The Cartesian components, F_i , of the force exerted by a stress field, p_{ij} , on a dislocation are[2]

$$F_i = - \epsilon_{ijk} t_j p_{kr} b_r, \quad (10)$$

where t_j are the components of the unit vector tangent to the dislocation in the positive sense, b_r are the components of the Burgers vector and ϵ_{ijk} are the components of the permutation tensor. If the dislocation shown in Figure 2 is an edge dislocation then we can write

$$\begin{aligned} b_i &= b \delta_{i2} \\ t_i &= \delta_{i1}, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where b is the magnitude of the Burgers vector. Substituting Eqns. (5) and (11) into Eqn. (10) we have

$$\begin{aligned} F_1 &= 0, \\ F_2 &= - \frac{R^3 p_y b y z}{[x^2 + y^2 + z^2]^{5/2}}, \\ F_3 &= - \frac{p_y b}{3} \left(\frac{R}{B} \right)^3 \left[2 + \frac{B^3}{[x^2 + y^2 + z^2]^{3/2}} - \frac{3B^3 y^2}{[x^2 + y^2 + z^2]^{5/2}} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

for the force per unit length on the edge dislocation. Since the deformation field of the particle is purely radial, the stress field in all such glide planes depends only on their radial distance, z , from the origin.

The glide force, F_2 , has a maximum value of

$$F_2^{\max} = - \frac{16}{\sqrt{3125}} \frac{R^3 p_y b z}{[x^2 + z^2]^2} \quad (13)$$

at

$$y = \pm \frac{\sqrt{x^2 + z^2}}{2}. \quad (14)$$

Clearly the maximum value of the force on the dislocation occurs at $x = 0$. Therefore the maximum shear stress required to drive this segment of the dislocation past the particle is

$$p_{\text{glide}} \geq - \frac{16}{\sqrt{3125}} p_y \left(\frac{R}{z} \right)^3 \quad (15)$$

where

$$b p_{\text{glide}} = F_2^{\max} \Big|_{x=0} \quad (16)$$

and the value of z in Eqn. (15) is subject to the bounds given by Eqn. (6). The maximum impedance to glide occurs in the glide planes that just touch the extremity of the yield zone, $z = R$, where from

Eqn. (15)

$$P_{\text{glide}}^{\text{max}} = - \frac{16}{\sqrt{3125}} P_y = 0.286 P_y \quad (17)$$

The corresponding average impedance to glide, again from Eqn. (15), becomes

$$P_{\text{glide}}^{\text{av}} = - \frac{16}{\sqrt{3125}} \frac{P_y R^3}{(B - R)} \int_R^B \frac{dz}{z^3} = 0.143 \frac{P_y R (B + R)}{B^2} \quad (18)$$

For a screw dislocation we can take

$$\begin{aligned} t_i &= \delta_{ii} , \\ b_i &= b \delta_{ii} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

in which case Eqn. (10) yields, from Eqns. (5) and (19):

$$\begin{aligned} F_1 &= 0 , \\ F_2 &= - \frac{R^3 P_y b x z}{[x^2 + y^2 + z^2]^{5/2}} , \\ F_3 &= \frac{R^3 P_y b x y}{[x^2 + y^2 + z^2]^{5/2}} . \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

The orientation of such a dislocation becomes unstable as it attempts to glide past a particle. That is, the motion of the region for which $x > 0$ is opposed and that of the $x < 0$ segment is assisted by the internal stress field. In order to pass by the particle the external stress must overcome the maximum value of the force opposing the motion of the dislocation. This maximum value is

$$F_2^{\text{max}} = - \frac{16}{\sqrt{3125}} \frac{R^3 P_y b z}{[y^2 + z^2]^2} \quad (21)$$

located along the dislocation at

$$x = \frac{\sqrt{y^2 + z^2}}{2} . \quad (22)$$

We thus see that the opposition to glide of the screw dislocation past the particle is precisely given by the edge dislocation result, Eqn. (15), that is, when $y = 0$ in Eqn. (21). The effect of these residual stresses is to increase the external stress required for plastic flow above that required to cause yielding of the unstressed matrix.

INTERACTION WITH CRACKS

To estimate the effect of the residual stresses given by Eqn (5) on fracture we now consider the plane at $x_3 = z$ in Figure 2 to be the plane of a Mode I crack and evaluate the average Mode I stress acting across the section of the composite sphere. From Eqn. (5) the normal stress acting on this plane is

$$p_{zz} = \frac{p_y}{3} \left(\frac{R}{B} \right)^3 \left\{ 2 + \frac{B^3}{[x^2 + y^2 + z^2]^{3/2}} \left[1 - \frac{3z^2}{[x^2 + y^2 + z^2]} \right] \right\}, \quad (23)$$

where x,y, and z are again subject to the bounds defined by Eqns. (9), (8) and (6), respectively. The average value of p_{33} in any such plane identified by the value of z is

$$p_{zz}^{av} = \frac{1}{\pi R_s^2} \int_0^{R_s} 2\pi R' p_{33}(R') dR', \quad (24)$$

where R_s is given by Eqn. (7) and $R' = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}$. Evaluating Eqn. (24) with p_{zz} given by Eqn. (23) reveals that the average stress is zero.

CONCLUSIONS

Calculations of the forces exerted by the residual stress field on dislocations indicate that residual stresses can impede the progress of both edge and screw dislocations through the unyielded region surrounding the particle and the plastic zone. The incremental force added by these stresses has the effect of increasing the yield stress of the unyielded matrix surrounding the plastic zone, hence it contributes a strengthening effect to the composite.

The maximum value of the incremental stress required to move a dislocation through the influence of the plastic zone is independent of the size of the plastic zone. This increment to the yield stress is 28% of the yield stress of the matrix in the absence of residual stress. The average value of the incremental stress does depend on the radius of the plastic zone and the radius of the stress-free outer surface of the spherical region surrounding the particle.

The average stress associated with Mode I crack propagation through the metal matrix adjacent to the yielded zone vanishes, hence it is not affected by the residual stress field. However, since the flow stress of the matrix should experience an increase, as noted above, we expect a decrease in fracture toughness to occur as a result of these residual stresses.

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